

Procedural Decomposition

Exercise 1: Guitar

Write a program to print three types of guitars on the screen using ASCII characters: a classical guitar, a guitar with a retro head, and a long guitar with a neck twice as long as the classical guitar. We have provided you with all the different print statements needed to draw the three types of guitars:

```
1 #classical guitar
2 print("    ___")
3 print("    o|* *|o")
4 print("    o|* *|o")
5 print("    o|* *|o")
6 print("    \===/")
7 print("    |||")
8 print("    |||")
9 print("    ___|||___")
10 print("  /    |||    \ ")
11 print(" /    |||    \ ")
12 print(" |    |||    |")
13 print(" \  (|||)  /")
14 print(" |    |||    |")
15 print(" /    |||    \ ")
16 print(" /    |||    \ ")
17 print(" /    |||    \ ")
18 print(" |    [===]    |")
19 print(" \                /")
20 print("  ' .                . '")
21 print("  '-----' ")
22 #retro head
23 print("    .-_-.")
24 print("    +|\G/|+")
25 print("    +|\./|+")
26 print("    +|\./|+")
27 print("    \===/")
28 #long neck
29 print("    \===/")
30 print("    |||")
31 print("    |||")
32 print("    |||")
33 print("    |||")
34 print("    ___|||___")
```

Your task is to split these statements between different functions and then combine them by calling them in the correct order. For code that is identical to the provided code indicate the line number or range, do NOT waste time copying it.

```
1 def print_head() -> None:
2     # lines 1-6
3
4 def print_retro_head() -> None:
5     # lines 23-27
6
7 def print_neck() -> None:
8     # lines 7-8
9
10 def print_body() -> None:
11     # lines 9-21
12
13 def print_classic_guitar() -> None:
14     print_head()
15     print_neck()
16     print_body()
17
18 def print_retro_guitar() -> None:
19     print_retro_head()
20     print_neck()
21     print_body()
22
23 def print_long_guitar() -> None:
24     print_head()
25     print_neck()
26     print_neck()
27     print_body()
28
29 def main() -> None:
30     print_classic_guitar()
31     print_retro_guitar()
32     print_long_guitar()
33
34 main()
```

Exercise 2: Old MacDonald Song

Write a program that outputs the lyrics for the children's song Old MacDonald Had a Farm:

```
1 Old MacDonald had a farm
2 Ee i ee i o
3 And on his farm he had some cows
4 Ee i ee i o
5 With a moo-moo here
6 And a moo-moo there
7 Here a moo, there a moo
8 Everywhere a moo-moo
9 Old MacDonald had a farm
10 Ee i ee i o
11 Old MacDonald had a farm
12 Ee i ee i o
13 And on his farm he had some chicks
14 Ee i ee i o
15 With a cluck-cluck here
16 And a cluck-cluck there
17 Here a cluck, there a cluck
18 Everywhere a cluck-cluck
19 Old MacDonald had a farm
20 Ee i ee i o
21 Old MacDonald had a farm
22 Ee i ee i o
23 And on his farm he had some pigs
24 Ee i ee i o
25 With a oink-oink here
26 And a oink-oink there
27 Here a oink, there a oink
28 Everywhere a oink-oink
29 Old MacDonald had a farm
30 Ee i ee i o
```

You want to use a smart design that reuses code statements as much as possible similarly to the previous problem. Which lines of the song are identical?

1, 9, 11, 19, 21, 29

2, 4, 10, 12, 14, 20, 22, 24, 30

Which lines of code are similar but not identical (identify what is different between them)?

3, 13, 23 (the animal is different: cows, chicks, pigs)

5-8, 15-18, 25-28 (the sound the animal makes if different: moo, cluck, oink)

To start off, define the headers for the utility functions you will be using in your program on the next page (leave space to write your code). Have your design checked by your instructor before you proceed. (Note that you should avoid designing functions with one line of code.) Next, implement each utility function and call it in the appropriate place in your program until

it produces the desired output. You may need to refine your design and refactor your code a few times before you have reached the optimal program.

```
1 def chorus() -> None:
2     print('Old MacDonald had a farm')
3     print('Ee i ee i o')
4
5 def makes_sound(sound) -> None:
6     sound_twice = sound + '-' + sound
7     print(f"With a {sound_twice} here")
8     print(f"And a {sound_twice} there")
9     print(f"Here a {sound}, there a {sound}")
10    print(f"Everywhere a {sound_twice}")
11
12 def song_part(animal, sound) -> None:
13    print(f"And on his farm he had some {animal}")
14    print('Ee i ee i o')
15    makes_sound(sound)
16
17 def main() -> None:
18    chorus()
19    song_part("cows", "moo")
20    chorus()
21    song_part("chicks", "cluck")
22    chorus()
23    song_part("pigs", "oink")
24    chorus()
25
26 main()
```

Exercise 3: Flower Buds and Stems

Write a program that prints all the combinations between flower buds and stems like this:

```
1 Long-stem Rose
2   @@@@
3  @@()@@
4   @@@@
5     Y
6     \|/
7    \|/
8   (((|)))
9 Short-stem Rose
10  @@@@
11 @@()@@
12  @@@@
13     Y
14     \|/
15   (((|)))
16 Short-stem Carnation
17 vVVVv
18 (___)
19     Y
20     \|/
21   (((|)))
22 Long-stem Carnation
23 vVVVv
24 (___)
25     Y
26     \|/
27    \|/
28   (((|)))
```

****Note** that we already provided you with the statements to print the different parts of a flower in comments.

- In the output above first identify lines that are repeated. The code statements corresponding to these lines will form a function in your program (also called an utility function).
- Next, pick names for the different utility functions identified in the previous step and write their headers in your program, like this `def [func_name] () -> None:` by replacing `[func_name]` with the function name of your choosing (make sure that the names are suggestive of the purpose of the function).
- For each utility function, un-comment and move its corresponding lines of code from the ones provided.

- Invoke (call) these utility functions inside main in the appropriate places until your code prints the desired output.

Exercise 4: One Little Elephant

Write a program that outputs the lyrics for the children's song One Little Elephant:

```
1 One little elephant went out to play,  
2 Upon a spider's web one day.  
3 He had such enormous fun,  
4 That he called for another elephant to come!  
5  
6 Two little elephants went out to play,  
7 Upon a spider's web one day.  
8 They had such enormous fun,  
9 That they called for another elephant to come!  
10  
11 Three little elephants went out to play,  
12 Upon a spider's web one day.  
13 They had such enormous fun,  
14 That they called for another elephant to come!  
15  
16 Four little elephants went out to play,  
17 Upon a spider's web one day.  
18 They had such enormous fun,  
19 That they called for another elephant to come!  
20  
21 Five little elephants went out to play,  
22 Upon a spider's web one day.  
23 The web went creak, the web went crack,  
24 And five little elephants came running back!
```

You want to use a smart design that reuses code statements as much as possible similarly to the previous problem.

Which lines of the song are identical?

2, 7, 12, 17, 22

Which lines of code are similar but not identical (identify what is different between them)?

2, 7, 12, 17, 22 (the count is different: one, two, three, four, five)
4-5, 9-10, 14-15, 19-20 (singular and plural nouns: he, they)

In `lab2_littleelephant.py` define the headers for the utility functions you will be using in your program. Have your design checked by the instructor or the TAs before you proceed. (Note that you should avoid designing functions with one line of code if possible.)

Implement each utility function and call it in the appropriate place in your program until it produces the desired output. You may need to refine your design and refactor your code a few times before you have reached the optimal program.

Exercise 5: Fish

Design a program that prints a fish. Make sure to define appropriate utility functions for the distinctive features (such as the tail, body and head).

```
vvv
 v
vvv
vvvvv
vvvvvvv
vvvvvvvvv
vvv vvv
 v  v
```

```
1 def draw_tail() -> None:
2     print('  vvv')
3     print('   v')
4 def draw_body() -> None:
5     print('  vvv')
6     print('  vvvvv')
7     print('  vvvvvvv')
8     print(' vvvvvvvvv')
9 def draw_head() -> None:
10    print(' vvv vvv')
11    print('  v  v')
12 def main() -> None:
13    draw_tail()
14    draw_body()
15    draw_head()
16 main()
```

Exercise 6: Rubik's Cubes

Redesign the following program, by moving all the provided code statements in functions for respective distinctive features and to increase re-usability (and reduce repetition). Your resulting program must also have a main function that is the entry point in your program (that is, it gets executed first).

```
1 cube_len = int(input("Cube length? "))
2 box_w = int(input("Box width? "))
3 box_h = int(input("Box height? "))
4 box_l = int(input("Box length? "))
5
6 fit_w = box_w // cube_len
7 fit_h = box_h // cube_len
8 fit_l = box_l // cube_len
9
10 print(str(fit_w)+" Rubik's cubes will fit width-wise.")
11 print(str(fit_h)+" Rubik's cubes will fit height-wise.")
12 print(str(fit_l)+" Rubik's cubes will fit length-wise.")
13
14 res = fit_w * fit_h * fit_l
15 print(str(res)+" Rubik's cubes will fit in that container.")
```

```
1 def get_fit(small: int, side: str) -> int:
2     large = int(input(f"Box {side}? "))
3     fit = large // small
4     print(f"{fit} Rubik's cubes will fit {side}-wise.")
5     return fit
6 def main() -> None:
7     cube_len = int(input("Cube length? "))
8     res = get_fit(cube_len, 'width') *
9           get_fit(cube_len, 'height') *
10          get_fit(cube_len, 'length')
11     print(str(res)+" Rubik's cubes will fit in that container.")
12 main()
```

Exercise 7: Tower

Design and implement a program that draws a particular text-art pattern (a tower):

```
  ||
  ||
  __{ }__
__{: :: :: :: :: :}__
| | | | | | | | | | | |
( _ ) ( _ ) ( _ ) ( _ )
  ( _ ) ( _ ) ( _ )
  ---- ] [ ----
    --- ] [ ---
      ||
      ||
  | % % % % % |
  | % % % % % |
  | % % % % % |
  | % % % % % |
  __{ }__
__{: :: :: :: :: :}__
| | | | | | | | | | | |
```

You must use separate functions for distinct features and to increase reusability while reducing repetition in your code. Note that there are distinct segments to the figure as well as repeated elements which lend themselves naturally to implementing as separate functions.

- Notice that the feature below the spire at the top is identical to the base of the tower.
- Notice that the spire at the top is identical in size to the stem in the middle.
- Overall, there are just 4 distinct features (spire, topshell/base, bottomshell, middle).

Exercise 8: Owls

Write a program that draws two owls sitting on a branch at a distance that is randomly picked between 5 and 20 (inclusive) spaces. One possible output could be:

```
.-".- .      .-".- .
/ 4 4 \      / 4 4 \
\_ v _/      \_ v _/
//  \ \      //  \ \
((    ))      ((    ))
=====
   | | |      | | |
```

Important Note: Printing the backslash character is tricky because python uses the backslash to produce special characters. For example, the string `\t` is a tab and `\n` is a newline. A single backslash character is represented by a string of two backslash characters (`\\`). For example:

```
print("\\\\")
```

will print:

```
\\
```

Exercise 9: Owls - extended

You may extend `Owls` to print multiple (3+) different looking owls together on a branch. Some examples of different looking owls are:

```
.---.
/ _ _ \
\_ v _/
//  \ \
((    ))
=====
   | | |
```

Sleeping, no crest, tucked feet owl

```
.-".- .
/ 6_6
\_ ( _ \
//  \ \
((    ))
=====
   | | |
```

Owl looking sideways

Exercise 10: Drive Times

You and your friends really enjoy the Fast and Furious movies and have started to race between Hamilton and Cazenovia (please don't do this). You are tasked with writing a program to calculate and analyze driving times for this race. Given the times of a certain number of drivers (entered by the user), your program should perform the following tasks:

- Input the drive times (all the drive times are entered at once, on a single line and separated by '|').
- Transform the drive times input from a '|'-separated string to a list of decimal values.
- Compute the average, fastest and slowest drive times. You must use the 'min' and 'max' built-in functions. You must NOT use the 'sum' function. Instead, you must use the accumulator pattern in order to compute the average drive time.
- Print the stats computed at the previous step.

Example program output ('25.5|28.0|23.0|22.9|27.6' is the input that the user enters):

```
Enter drive times (|-separated): 25.5|28.0|23.0|22.9|27.6
Average drive time: 25.40 seconds
Fastest drive: 22.90 seconds
Slowest drive: 28.00 seconds
```

Exercise 11: Taxes

It is tax season and you are looking for a way to hone in your newly acquired programming skills, so you get a job with a local accounting firm. Your first assignment is to implement a program that is able to calculate the tax bracket and amount of tax that must be paid for different incomes of individuals filling separately. Here is the 2024 Tax Bracket:

Bracket	Rate	Taxable Income Separately	Taxable Income Jointly
1	10%	Up to \$11,000	Up to \$22,000
2	12%	\$11,001 to \$44,725	\$22,001 to \$89,450
3	22%	\$44,726 to \$95,375	\$89,451 to \$190,750
4	24%	\$95,376 to \$182,100	\$190,751 to \$364,200
5	32%	\$182,101 to \$231,250	\$364,201 to \$462,500
6	35%	\$231,251 to \$346,875	\$462,501 to \$693,750
7	37%	Over \$346,876	Over \$693,751

You must implement a user interface function that asks a user for their income. If the income is less or equal to 0 then it prints 'Invalid income amount' and ends the program. Otherwise, it then asks the user whether they want to know the bracket rate or the tax they owe.

Below are four examples of inputs and corresponding expected outputs:

```
What is your income? 0
Invalid income amount
```

```
What is your income? 30000.0
Enter r for bracket rate and t for tax: t
You owe $3380.0 in federal taxes
```

```
What is your income? 525600
Enter r for bracket rate and t for tax: r
Your tax bracket rate is 37%
```

```
What is your income? 525600
Enter r for bracket rate and t for tax: s
Invalid option
```

Exercise 12: Taxes - extended

Adapt the program for taxes to also work for individuals filling jointly.

Exercise 13: Midterm Question

We are providing you with the correct code statements to read a random number of data points (for between 5 and 10 participants) from the user input and then compute and print both the average and standard deviation for this data subset.

```
1 import random
2 import math

4 participant_count = random.randint(5,10)

6 #read data
7 data=[]
8 for step in range(participant_count):
9     new_data = input('Input data: ')
10    data.append(int(new_data))
11 print(f'You entered this data: {data}')

13 #compute average
14 sum=0
15 for value in data:
16     sum += value
17 average = sum / len(data)
18 print(f'The average of this data is {average}')

20 #compute standard dev
21 sum_diff=0
22 for value in data:
23     sum_diff += (value - average)**2
24 std_dev = math.sqrt(sum_diff / (len(data) - 1))
25 print(f'The std dev of this data is {std_dev}')
```

Your task is to come up with an optimal design and split the provided code statements across different functions. **Note that you are not allowed to modify the code statements that we have provided you with.** Additionally, **DO NOT** put code outside of functions (e.g., do not use global variables). To get you started we have provided you with a skeleton that already uses code statements 1, 2, 4, 11, 18, and 25. You must name, define and use functions, as well as indicate which provided code statements need to go on which line inside respective functions. You may write only the line numbers (e.g., 5) below, or write out the code.

```
import random 1
import math 2
def
```

```
def
```

```
def
```

```
def main() -> None:
    participant_count = random.randint(5,10) 4
```

```
    print(f'You entered this data: {data}') 11
    print(f'The average of this data is {average}') 18
    print(f'The std dev of this data is {std_dev}') 25
main()
```